

188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science

Exercise 2 - Reproduce experiment results from a paper

Mal Kurteshi

11924480

e11924480@student.tuwien.ac.at

Muhamet Kaçuri

11946223

e11946223@student.tuwien.ac.at

Ylli Parduzi

12014533

e12014533@student.tuwien.ac.at

In this report we are presenting the reproduce of the results obtained in the paper "Domain-Independent Extraction of Scientific Concepts from Research Articles" by Arthur Brack, Jennifer D'Souza, Anett Hoppe, Sören Auer and Ralph Ewerth. The reason of picking this paper to reproduce its results is because of the interesting content of the paper where lots of insights can be obtained.

1 Experiment description

The experiment presented in the paper deals with a very interesting topic on how to get information from different scientific sources and then classify the papers in proper fields of science, art or music. This is done first by collection and analyze of the abstract of the papers and then by using different features and evaluations from Supervised learning and Active learning techniques in order to full fill the classification process with high accuracy as possible.

2 Data and information extraction

The data and information is collected from different search engines such as Google Scholar, Microsoft Academics, Semantic Scholar quite specific and specialized in publications and scholar literature. The information is exploited from the graph algorithms used in these search engines. The abstract or introduction section from different papers in different fields is taken and stored into text files firstly in order to latter process with concept extraction in proper manner for the models of classification.

3 Concept-Extraction

As of a concept extraction in this paper an exploration of domain independent annotation of lexical phrasal unit indicating scientific knowledge such as scientific concept in abstracts of papers and then see how well a deep learning model

such as SciBERT, performs on information extraction task and whether active learning can help to reduce the amount of required training data. SciBert word embeddings are pre-trained on scientific texts using the BERT algorithm. Also two approaches were used for this concept extraction such as supervised learning and also active learning. [1]

3.1 Supervised learning

By the SciBert algorithm first one model with data from all domains is combined. Then similarly 10 train models are created for each domain in our scope of work. In order to obtain a robust evaluation also after the models creation a 5-fold cross validation is performed in the experiment. So for each fold a model was trained for 8 abstracts for domain and a hyperparameter tuning on 1 abstract per domain then test on the remaining 2 abstracts per domain. We need also to pay attention that the data splits are not the same in between folds. [1]

3.2 Active learning

Also an active learning approach to train new domain-independent classifier was applied using the MNLP sampling strategy taking into consideration the less computational requirements. MNLP does greedy sampling of text giving preferences to the least logarithmic likelihood of the predicted tag sequence by the decoder, normalized in order to avoid big text processings. The paper experiment has shown that adding 4 percent of the data to be the most discriminative selection of classifier performance then a five-fold cross validation was performed. [1]

4 Reproducing of Results

First we started to install the required packages in order to run the problem and create a suitable environment. During the process of the package installation and requirements

we have faced a problem that some of the packages for this specific project were not available to be used in Windows 10 operating system which was the system that we had in the beginning.

As a temporary solution for this issue we have decided to do a virtual machine in our environment in order to continue further with the reproduction of this project. In this matter we have installed and configured the Linux Mint operating system in which we were able to successfully install all the requirement packages.

Considering that our task in the experiment is a classification task we have decided firstly to separate the raw data into different fields for classification based on their content of their abstract, these fields were of different types like :

1. Agriculture
2. Astronomy
3. Biology
4. Chemistry
5. Computer science
6. Earth science
7. Engineering
8. Materials science
9. Mathematics
10. Medicine
11. overall

After this separation we proceeded with the hyperparameter tuning phase.

4.1 Data split

Before processing with any other action we have decided to have a separation on the data in three different sets in order to have the validity of the model as accurate as possible.

The dataset was split in the format as presented below:

1. Train 60%
2. Test 20%
3. Dev 20%

4.2 Hyperparameters tuning Statistical testing

In the hyperparameters tuning phase we have decided to perform a 5 fold cross validation in order to obtain the best parameters for hyperparameter tuning such as best learning rate, dropout and LSTM hidden size for all domains and overall classifier. This was performed for each separation that we had mentioned earlier.

Important to note that for each fold a file was created with specific parameters, these parameters needed to be validated and to obtain the best parameters overall.

In the table below we can see the results for the best hyperparameter tuning.

domain	best hyperparams	folds	dev-f1-allen	dev-f1-allen-std	test-f1-allen	test-f1-allen-std
Agriculture	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_200_lr_0.005	5	0.6565827	0.062345831	0.609343493	0.052836397
Astronomy	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_500_lr_0.005	5	0.673840249	0.055423262	0.609207107	0.052372218
Biology	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_500_lr_0.005	5	0.657381348	0.085683106	0.723547566	0.074809885
Chemistry	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_350_lr_0.005	5	0.76595895	0.105052975	0.53425417	0.078568753
Computer Science	dr_0.2_lstm_hs_350_lr_0.005	5	0.61407425	0.106725016	0.438215977	0.04216261
Earth Science	dr_0.2_lstm_hs_200_lr_0.005	5	0.53205063	0.0712719	0.464181179	0.050263829
Engineering	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_768_lr_0.005	5	0.6523595	0.093483134	0.643685463	0.031499568
Materials Science	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_350_lr_0.005	5	0.637490229	0.084520676	0.653214909	0.107373495
Mathematics	dr_0.2_lstm_hs_768_lr_0.001	5	0.613571191	0.185309885	0.310947823	0.056532879
Medicine	dr_0.2_lstm_hs_200_lr_0.005	5	0.653821344	0.185734201	0.56284889	0.081286575
overall	dr_0.5_lstm_hs_768_lr_0.005	5	0.626834263	0.023896984	0.659012203	0.010235812

In the table we can see the best hyperparameters file also the metrics used for statistical testing. In order to provide which parameters were the best a statistical testing of F1 score for different splits was used.

4.3 Prediction

After getting the data and splitting them into subsets for the training models and defining the best hyperparameters for the models, our aim was to obtain as close as possible the values presented in the paper which we are mentioning here also in the figure below:

	PROCESS	METHOD	MATERIAL	DATA	Overall
<i>P</i>	65.5 (±4.22)	45.8 (±13.50)	69.2 (±3.55)	60.3 (±4.14)	64.3 (±1.73)
<i>R</i>	68.3 (±1.93)	44.1 (±8.73)	73.2 (±4.27)	60.0 (±4.84)	66.7 (±0.92)
<i>F1</i>	66.8 (±2.07)	43.0 (±6.30)	71.0 (±1.88)	59.8 (±1.75)	65.5 (±1.26)

[2]

At this stage of the modeling stage we started to have problems with the prediction algorithm such as SciBERT and MNLP. First of all the problems that we encountered that the prediction script couldn't find some files related to the data and to the structure of the algorithm.

First we thought that this could be by any chance that we have skipped any step of the documentation to be able to produce the prediction from the algorithms.

But after analyse and carefully checking and re running the code we identified that there are some features of the algorithms such as json files in order to populate the prediction sets where missing, these files are not produced by the earlier steps that we had to execute according to documentation.

This led us into a stuck of the prediction step and the evaluation step since we couldn't realise the prediction phase we were not able to reproduce the specific obtaining results provided in this paper. In this point we started to think about other alternatives and other potential data prediction algorithms for classification.

4.4 Alternatives

In this section we are presenting the alternatives of the data algorithm predictions tried in this reproducing process.

Knowing that our task was a classification task we decided to look at the some other classification algorithms that might have been suitable for this purpose. The algorithms that were tried in this phase were algorithms such as Decision Trees, Random Forest and SVM.

Important to note that our dataset consist of categorical features and of lots of words together and taking into consideration that the mentioned classification algorithms require a preprocess of data before we use them and since the data is categorical we have to do a 1-N encoding, which in or case also excluded the use of these algorithms taking into consid-

eration that the mapping of words in to different categories led us into a big dataset with very time complexity to process turning this experiment into a very computationally expensive case.

5 Conclusions

In the section we are presenting the conclusions obtained in our attempt to represent the results from the paper "Domain-Independent Extraction of Scientific Concepts from Research Articles".

First choosing the domain for the reproduce process is very sensitive, in the manner that some fields of studies may require special and very strong environment in order to reproduce the results never the less the paper was very interesting also the use of advanced algorithms such as SciBert and MNLP was very challenging.

Important to note that working with big text data is very hard to preprocess if we are trying to use some random classification algorithms such as Decision trees, Random Forest or SVM's, this is due to one hot encoding leading us to a very large not manageable dataset.

The reproducible process went good for the hyperparameter optimization and train and test splitting but leading us to a stuck in the algorithm prediction phase. For the Hyperparameters we were able to reproduce good results and also for the data preparation of the algorithms SciBert and MNLP a good achievement was obtained but for the prediction phase we were not able to reproduce the result presented in the paper.

References

- [1] ARTHUR BRACK, JENNIFER D'SOUZA, A. H. S. A., AND EWERTH, R. Domain-independent extraction of scientific concepts from research articles.
- [2] BRACK, A. Stm-corpus. <https://gitlab.com/TIBHannover/orkg/orkg-nlp/tree/master/STM-corpus>, 2020.